

School Heads' Practices and Skills in Financial Management in Relation to Teachers' Performance

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Abstract:

Financial management is a critical aspect of school leadership, ensuring the efficient allocation of resources, transparency in budgeting, and sustainability of institutional operations. In the Philippines, school heads are responsible for overseeing financial planning, monitoring expenditures, and ensuring compliance with government regulations. However, the extent to which their financial management skills influence teachers' performance remains an area that requires further exploration. Existing studies highlight the importance of financial literacy and management among school heads (Delmo, et al., 2023). This study aimed to determine the levels of School Heads financial management practices and skills in relation to the level of teacher's performance in a cluster of a medium-sized schools divisions in central Philippines for School Year 2024-2025. Using descriptive analytical scheme, the study made use of 249 teachers as respondents, who were asked to take a self-made, fully validated questionnaire. School Heads financial management practices and skills were measured in terms of planning and budgeting, resource allocation, financial resource mobilization and financial accountability and governance. The findings of the study showed that majority of the respondents belong to the younger category and almost two-thirds have no post graduate degrees. Majority of them are less tenured. The level of school heads' financial management practices and skills were both high. The study further revealed that there is a significant difference in both levels of financial management practices, as well as with their skills. In terms of teachers' performance, there was no significant difference. Finally, the study revealed no significant relationship between financial management practices and financial managements skills; also, there was no significant relationship between the level of school heads' financial management practices and the level of teacher's performance; as well as no significant relationship the level of school heads' financial management practices and the level of teacher's performance.

Keywords: Financial management practices and skills, School Heads, teachers' performance

Introduction:

Nature of the Problem

Financial management is a critical aspect of school leadership, ensuring the efficient allocation of resources, transparency in budgeting, and sustainability of institutional operations. In the Philippines, school heads are responsible for overseeing financial planning, monitoring expenditures, and ensuring compliance with government regulations. However, the extent to which their financial management skills influence teachers' performance remains an area that requires further exploration. Existing studies highlight the importance of financial literacy and management among school heads (Delmo, et al., 2023).

According to Alvarez and Potane (2024), school leaders in the Philippines show great skill in financial management practices, but they struggle with issues like stakeholder participation, transparency, and budget distribution. In the same thought, Wadasen (2024) noted that school leaders frequently struggle with slow fund distribution, inadequate training, and poor financial management. These problems might have an impact on teachers' overall job happiness, access to materials, and chances for professional growth.

Although financial management is widely acknowledged as a crucial administrative task, there has been little study on its direct effects on teacher performance. Although Mirando and Jalos (2023) examined financial management

strategies connected to the Basic Education Learning Continuity Plan (BE-LCP), they did not investigate the impact of these practices on teaching efficacy.

With the present situation in the educational landscape of the country, including low budget for schools, delayed funding release, and the urgent need for transparency, this study aimed to determine the relationship between school heads' financial management skills and teachers' performance. This study seeks to explore further into best financial management practices, policy formulations, and leadership strategies that can improve financial governance in schools and enhance teachers' performance.

Current State of Knowledge

As the head administrator, a school principal is in charge of overseeing the entire school community, which consists of employees, students, and families. Since it guarantees that everyone is aware of the school's objective and their part in it, communication is crucial to the work. The principal of the school is in charge of all day-to-day activities and operations. The principle is in charge of making sure that staff and students can learn in a secure setting. All facets of the profession require excellent communication skills. Being a school leader requires you to have firsthand knowledge of what it's like to teach in a classroom (Dayton, 2021). The subject one teaches to prepare for the role of principal is not as important as the experience gained while handling all the responsibilities of a teacher (Dayton, 2021).

One of the industries in the nation that needs a significant amount of funding is education. Enrollment in schools has increased nationally since the implementation of the Universal Basic Education program, particularly at the junior secondary school level. The federal, state, and municipal governments all spend a significant amount of money on it every year as a result. Since then, it has been argued that voluntary organizations are necessary to support government efforts in funding and managing monies. Accordingly, the Federal Republic of Nigeria asserted that since education is a costly social service and needs sufficient funding from all levels of government to be implemented successfully, she welcomes and encourages local communities, individuals, and other organizations to contribute to the education sector (Nwafukwa, 2016).

As the school's financial manager, school heads should be able to discover different funding sources to support academic and extracurricular programs on a daily basis. The most crucial prerequisite for the successful execution of curricula and the provision of high-quality education is the capacity to produce sufficient financial resources. This can be accomplished through well-established and coordinated school-based revenue-generating initiatives, such as renting school assets like buildings, cars, and playgrounds to nearby communities that require them in order to raise extra money (Amos & Koda, 2018).

Throughout the history of education, the idea that principals affect the school has been consistent. The principal is a major contributor to the school's performance, according to numerous studies on school reform over the years. The principle shapes the learning environment by clearly communicating the school's vision and mission. Since the vision and mission provide direction and purpose, this is a critical component of teacher and student success (Kambeya, 2017).

The study of Merano (2023) investigated the financial management competence of elementary school heads and the performance of schools in Leyte Division. The research involved 70 school heads and 369 teachers involved in the School Financial Task Force for the 2016-2017 school year. The findings revealed that most school heads are middle-aged with low family income and lack training in school financial management. Their enrollment and instructor populations are limited, and they oversee a variety of financial resources. Few school heads are less competent than the majority in the areas of asset management, accounting, budgeting, and procurement. Competency in asset management is correlated with family income and the quantity of trainings completed. The scores of the National Achievement Test are mediocre, and school performance has nothing to do with how well school administrators handle finances. According to the report, school heads should participate in training and seminars on school finance management that integrate community involvement and school planning teams. All school activities must be financed through efficient use of the school's financial resources.

On the one hand, Espinosa (2019) examined the growth of any educational sector while taking into account the administration of its finances, as well as the performance of the teachers who were employed by General Santos City's public high schools. By analyzing the participants' perceptions, attitudes, understanding, knowledge, values, feelings, and experiences regarding their schools' financial management, a qualitative research design employing a phenomenological approach revealed how teachers, as participants, interpret financial management at their institutions. Six people participated in the focus group discussion, while eleven people participated in the in-depth interview. All of the study's participants are currently employed as teachers in General Santos City's government schools. The findings showed that school heads' financial management strategies aid in budget creation, goal-setting, and the identification of sources for human resources, time, instructional materials, and proper costing. It would be

extremely important if school leaders like principals received ongoing professional development support by gaining the necessary financial skills and abilities to manage resources in the school. This would allow them to manage financial resources more responsively to the performance and instructional needs of the teachers.

Theoretical Underpinnings

This study is grounded on the Agency Theory by Stephen Ross and Barry Mitnick (1973) to account for the school heads' financial management skills and the Leader-Member Exchange (LMX) Theory (Graen & Uhl-Bien, 1995). A principal and an agent's connection and how to align their financial interests are examined by the agency theory of economics. The theory is frequently utilized in the fields of corporate management, governance, and finance. The owner of a business is the principal, and the person in charge of managing it is the agent. This theory's central idea is the Principal and the Agent. Corporate directors, for instance, are the agent while stockholders are the principal. According to agency theory, a company's value cannot be maximized if its agents are not adequately supervised or incentivized. Similar grounding situations occur between school heads and officials, when the decision-maker (heads) may decide to distribute resources in a different way than other officials or subordinates may wish. However, depending on the school's objective and vision, accountability and supervision responsibilities may still align their interests, even disagreements among school authorities regarding the location or method of resource allocation. This theory does a good job of describing how school administrators probably handle school resources. Additionally, the idea suggests that strong leader-member relationships facilitate efficient financial decision-making, guaranteeing that educators have access to the tools they need for instruction, professional growth, and rewards. School administrators can more effectively prioritize budgetary decisions that improve teaching effectiveness and work happiness when they cultivate excellent relationships with teachers. Strong leader-member interactions lead to open communication and mutual trust, claims LMX Theory. Teachers are more likely to trust institutional regulations and provide a stable learning environment if school administrators show accountability and transparency in financial management.

Objectives

This study aimed to determine the levels of School Heads financial management practices and skills in relation to the level of teacher's performance in a cluster of a medium-sized schools divisions in central Philippines for School Year 2024-2025. Specifically, this study seeks to answer the following questions: 1) determine the profile of the respondents in terms of age, highest educational attainment and length of service, 2) determine the level of school heads' financial management practices according to planning and budgeting, resource allocation, financial resource mobilization, and financial accountability and governance; 3) determine the level of school heads' financial management skills according to the aforementioned areas; 4) determine the level of teacher's performance when grouped according to aforementioned variables; 5) determine if there is a significant difference in the level of school heads' financial management practices when grouped and compared according to aforementioned variables; 6) determine if there is a significant difference in the level of school heads' financial management skills when grouped and compared according to aforementioned variables; 7) determine if there is a significant difference in the level of teacher's performance when grouped and compared according to aforementioned variables; 8) determine if there is a significant relationship between level of school heads' financial management practices and skills; 9) determine if there is a significant relationship between level of school heads' financial management practices and the level of teacher's performance; and 10) determine if there is a significant relationship between level of school heads' financial management skills and the level of teacher's performance.

Methodology:

This section presents the discussion of the research methodology used, the subjects and respondents of the study, the research instruments used, the validity and reliability of the instruments, the procedure for data gathering, and the statistical tools and procedure for data analysis.

Research Design

This study used descriptive research design to determine the level of School Heads financial management practices and skills in relation to the level of teacher's performance in a cluster of a medium-sized schools divisions in central Philippines for School Year 2024-2025. According to Ary (2017), descriptive research involves collecting data in order to test hypotheses or to answer questions concerning the current status of the subject of the study. A descriptive study determines and reports the way things are. Descriptive research is scientific research that describes about event, phenomena or fact systematically dealing with certain area or population.

Study Respondents

The respondents of the study were the 249 teachers from medium-sized division in central Philippines. Since the number of respondents is quite large to handle, stratified sampling and random sampling technique was used and

using Cochran formula to find the sample size. The respondents were randomly selected by the researcher from each section using the lottery technique.

Instruments

To determine the level of school heads' financial management and financial practices in relation to teachers' performance this study made use of a self-made data gathering instrument which was subjected to Validity (5.00 - excellent) and Reliability testing (0.891 for financial management practices and 0.883 for financial management skills; both interpreted as "acceptable"). The questionnaire consisted of two parts: Part 1 gathered the respondents' socio-economic information, such as age, highest educational attainment and length of service. Part 2 contained a total of 40 line-items. There were 20-line items for financial management practices and another 20 line-items for the financial management skills.

Data Gathering Procedure

In order to collect the data, written communications asking permission to conduct the study was sent to the Schools Division Superintendent. The purpose of the letter was to provide the SDO and the SDS a proper heads-up as to the purpose of the study, when and how the study will be conducted. The data gathering instrument was administered after the approval was secured and the copies of the instrument were retrieved after 3days After the collection of data, they were organized for statistical interpretation.

Data Analysis and Statistical Treatment

Objective No. 1 used descriptive analytical scheme and the statistical tools used were Frequency Count and Percentage Count to determine the profile of the respondents in terms of age, highest educational attainment and length of service.

Objective No. 2 also used descriptive analytical scheme and the statistical tool used was Mean to determine the level of school heads' financial management practices according to planning and budgeting, resource allocation, financial resource mobilization, and financial accountability and governance.

Objective No. 3 also used descriptive analytical scheme and the statistical tool used was Mean to determine the level of school heads' financial management skills according to planning and budgeting, resource allocation, financial resource mobilization, and financial accountability and governance.

Objective No. 4 still used descriptive analytical scheme and the statistical tool used was Mean to determine the level of teachers' performance when grouped according to aforementioned variables.

Objective No. 5 used comparative analytical scheme and the statistical tool was Mann-Whitney U test, to determine if there is a significant difference in the level of school heads' financial management practices when grouped and compared according to aforementioned variables.

Objective No. 6 used comparative analytical scheme and the statistical tool was Mann-Whitney U test, to determine if there is a significant difference in the level of school heads' financial management skills when grouped and compared according to aforementioned variables.

Objective No 7 also used comparative analytical scheme and the statistical tool was Mann-Whitney U test, to determine if there is a significant difference in the level of teacher's performance when grouped and compared according to aforementioned variables.

Objective No 8 used relational analytical scheme and the statistical tool used was Spearman rho to determine if there was a significant relationship in the level of teacher's performance when grouped and compared according to aforementioned variables.

Objective No 9 also used relational analytical scheme and the statistical tool used was Spearman rho to determine if there was a significant relationship between level of school heads' financial management practices and the level of teacher's performance.

Objective No. 10 still used relational analytical scheme and the statistical tool used was Spearman rho to determine if there was a significant relationship between level of school heads' financial management skills and the level of teacher's performance.

Ethical Consideration

Key ethical principles guiding the use of human participants and minors were strictly adhered to in the study. These included providing the teachers, parents, and students with the necessary information to make a determination as to whether they want (the students) to be part of the study. The signing of the consent form, which is actually a process rather than an event was not used as coercive tool to compel participants to complete the study. They were assured of their right to withdraw from the study at any point when they became uncomfortable with the study. The identity of the children as well as their responses was kept confidential such that neither the responses nor their identity was revealed to any other person outside the research team.

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Results and Discussion:

This section deals with the presentation, analysis and interpretation of data gathered to carry out the objectives of this study. All these were made possible by following certain appropriate procedures so as to give the exact data and solution to each specific problem.

Profile of the Respondents According to the Variables Age, Highest Educational Attainment, and Length of Service

Table 1
Profile of Respondents

Variables	Categories	Frequency	Percentage
Age	Younger (less than 37 years old)	135	54.20
	Older (37 years old and above)	114	45.80
	Total	249	100
Highest Educational Attainment	Lower (Bachelor Degree)	161	64.70
	Higher (Post Grad Level)	88	35.30
	Total	249	100
Length of Service	Shorter (less than 8 years)	136	54.60
	Longer (8 years and above)	113	45.40
	Total	249	100

There were 249 respondents, grouped according to age, highest educational attainment, and length of service. The age distribution reveals that a slightly higher proportion of school heads (54.20%) are younger (less than 37 years old) compared to their older counterparts (45.80%). As to highest educational attainment, majority (64.70%) hold a bachelor’s degree, while only 35.30% have pursued postgraduate studies. The length of service data shows that 54.60% of school heads have served for less than eight years, while 45.40% have eight years or more of experience. This distribution indicates a mix of experienced administrators alongside newer school heads. While fresh leadership may introduce dynamic strategies, seasoned administrators bring stability, institutional knowledge, and refined management skills. Bridging this gap through mentorship programs and structured leadership training can foster collaborative growth and effective succession planning.

Descriptive Analysis in the Level of School Heads’ Financial Management Practices in Planning Budgeting, Resource Allocation, Financial Resource Mobilization, and Financial Accountability and Governance

Table 2
Level of School Heads’ Financial Management Practices in Planning Budgeting

Area		
A. Planning and Budgeting	Mean	Interpretation
<i>The School Head ...</i>		
1. encourages the participation of all stakeholders in the planning and budget allocation	4.16	High Level
2. prioritizes academic needs over the school's physical development.	4.27	High Level
3. talks to every department head to ensure that their financial needs are allocated accordingly.	3.94	High Level
4. holds a consultative meeting with teachers, students and parents to ensure balanced allocation of funds.	4.37	High Level
5. creates a culture of openness in budget allocation.	4.40	High Level
Overall Mean	4.23	High Level

The findings indicate that the area of "talks to every department head to ensure that their financial needs are allocated accordingly" received the lowest mean (3.94, high level); while school heads exhibit strong financial planning and budgeting skills, this relatively lower score suggests potential gaps in department-level consultations that could lead to imbalanced fund distribution or unmet financial needs. Alvarez & Potane (2024) highlighted those transparent financial discussions improve institutional performance, emphasizing that structured budget dialogues help align financial allocations with school priorities. Similarly, Cristina et al. (2018) found that schools where department heads actively participate in financial planning tend to optimize resource distribution more effectively, ensuring balanced fund allocation across all departments. Given these implications, it is essential for school heads to implement structured consultation meetings, allowing department leaders to present their financial needs and justify budgetary allocations. Furthermore, establishing a standardized financial request system can streamline funding requests, preventing inconsistencies in resource distribution.

Table 3
Level of School Heads' Financial Management Practices in Resource Allocation

Area		
B. Resource Allocation	Mean	Interpretation
<i>The School Head ...</i>		
1. leads in the planning of all resource allocation efforts	4.43	High Level
2. empowers teachers and other officers in sharing resource allocation responsibilities.	4.26	High Level
3. manages school resources in accordance with DepEd Policies, accounting and auditing rules.	4.25	High Level
4. focuses on the spending of resources based on agreed projections.	4.18	High Level
5. ensures additional steps to avoid wastage of resources.	3.88	High Level
Overall Mean	4.20	High Level

The findings indicate that the item which states that "The school head ensures additional steps to avoid wastage of resources" received the lowest mean (3.88, high level); while school heads demonstrate strong overall proficiency in resource allocation, this relatively lower score suggests potential gaps in implementing effective waste reduction strategies within school financial operations. The lowest mean in this area implies that resource utilization may not be fully optimized, leading to unnecessary expenditures or misallocation of funds. Schools may face challenges in monitoring consumption patterns, enforcing cost-efficient spending, or maximizing resource lifespan. Alvarez & Potane (2024) emphasized that effective resource management requires rigorous oversight and structured financial planning, highlighting the need for monitoring mechanisms to prevent inefficiencies. Similarly, Espiritu (2020) noted that financial accountability improves when institutions implement clear guidelines for tracking expenditures and reducing waste.

Table 4
Level of School Heads' Financial Management Practices in Financial Resource Mobilization

Area		
C. Financial Resource Mobilization	Mean	Interpretation

The School Head ...

1. involve teachers, department heads, and other stakeholders in the resource allocation process to identify needs and ensure buy-in.	4.38	High Level
2. balances the needs of the school with available budget considering all other constraints.	4.56	Very High Level
3. communicates resource allocation decisions clearly to staff and stakeholders.	4.53	Very High Level
4. regularly reviews resource allocation strategies to adapt to changing needs.	4.00	High Level
5. monitors how resource allocations are being used and evaluating their impact on student learning.	4.35	High Level
Overall Mean	4.36	High Level

The results showed that in the area of resource mobilization, the item that states "The school head regularly reviews resource allocation strategies to adapt to changing needs" received the lowest mean (4.00, high level). The lowest mean in this area implies that resource allocation strategies may not be updated frequently enough to reflect evolving institutional demands, possibly leading to inefficiencies in budgeting or missed opportunities for financial optimization. Alvarez & Potane (2024) emphasized that regular financial reviews enhance resource efficiency, ensuring that budget allocations remain aligned with institutional goals. Similarly, Espiritu (2020) found that adaptive financial strategies contribute to long-term sustainability, particularly in schools undergoing organizational transitions.

Table 5

Level of School Heads' Financial Management Practices in Financial Accountability and Governance

Area	Mean	Interpretation
D. Financial Accountability		
<i>The School Head ...</i>		
1. practices full transparency in the submission of the school's financial report.	4.29	High Level
2. provides measures for timely submission of liquidation reports.	4.51	Very High Level
3. leads the school community in ensuring ethical practices in reporting every school expense.	4.33	High Level
4. reports all donations to the school pursuant to RA 9155.	4.31	High Level
5. ensures that the school financial report reflects academic priorities.	3.94	High Level
Overall Mean	4.28	High Level

The results showed that in terms of financial accountability and governance practices, the item which states that "The school heads ensures that the school financial report reflects academic priorities" got the lowest mean of 3.94, high level. The lower mean in this area implies that financial reports may not consistently highlight academic priorities, potentially leading to imbalanced funding distribution between administrative expenses and educational investments. Schools may face difficulties in clearly linking budget allocations to curriculum development, teacher training, and student support programs, which are essential for institutional growth. According to Ozer et al. (2023), timely and transparent financial reporting enhances stakeholder trust and decision-making, reinforcing the need for structured financial documentation that prioritizes academic needs. Similarly, Kaiser & Lusardi (2024) emphasized that financial literacy and education play a crucial role in ensuring that financial decisions align with institutional goals, suggesting that school heads may benefit from targeted financial training to strengthen budget alignment with academic priorities.

Descriptive Analysis in the Level of School Heads' Financial Management Skills in Planning Budgeting, Resource Allocation, Financial Resource Mobilization, and Financial Accountability and Governance

Table 6

Level of School Heads' Financial Management Skills in Planning Budgeting

Area	Mean	Interpretation
A. Planning and Budgeting		
<i>The School Head ...</i>		

1. spearheads all efforts to improve school funding by exploring all other remedies available for the school.	4.06	High Level
2. takes lead control of the planning and budgeting of the school.	4.45	High Level
3. empowers teachers by allowing them to submit budgetary requirements for their MOOE utilization.	4.23	High Level
4. aligns every cent of the school's budget with its academic objectives.	4.21	High Level
5. puts emphasis on the budgetary requirements for the school's ICT needs.	4.32	High Level
Overall Mean	4.25	High Level

The findings indicate that among the financial management skills assessed in planning and budgeting, the item "spearheads all efforts to improve school funding by exploring all other remedies available for the school" received the lowest mean (4.06, high level). The lowest mean in this area implies that school heads may primarily rely on traditional funding streams, such as government subsidies and internal school resources, rather than actively seeking external grants, sponsorships, or community partnerships to enhance financial sustainability. Adejola (2025) highlighted that strategic financial planning and diversified funding sources contribute to long-term institutional stability, reinforcing the importance of proactive fundraising and financial resource mobilization.

Table 7
Level of School Heads' Financial Management Skills in Resource Allocation

Area		
B. Resource Allocation	Mean	Interpretation
<i>The School Head ...</i>		
1. controls expenses for school-based training that are designed in most crucial needs.	4.30	High Level
2. allocate funds for the repair of facilities, building and ground maintenance of the school.	4.28	High Level
3. monitors proper utilization of the MOOE.	4.25	High Level
4. ensures low-cost but efficient allocation purchases of school resources.	4.38	High Level
5. ensures that the utilization of resources produces desired results.	4.02	High Level
Overall Mean	4.24	High Level

The table revealed that in financial management skills, the item that states "ensures that the utilization of resources produces desired results" received the lowest mean of 4.02, high level. School heads demonstrate strong proficiency in financial management however, slightly lower score suggests potential gaps in measuring the effectiveness of allocated resources and ensuring that expenditures translate into meaningful outcomes for school improvement. The lowest mean in this area implies that while resources are being allocated, their direct impact on institutional goals, such as teacher development, student learning, or infrastructure efficiency, may not always be systematically evaluated. According to Zhang & Sun (2024), effective financial oversight must include performance evaluations to ensure that funds contribute to measurable improvements, reinforcing the importance of data-driven financial assessments. Likewise, Adejola (2025) emphasized that resource allocation strategies should incorporate structured impact evaluations, ensuring that financial decisions support institutional effectiveness.

Table 8
Level of School Heads' Financial Management Skills in Financial Resource Mobilization

Area		
C. Financial Resource Mobilization	Mean	Interpretation
<i>The School Head ...</i>		
1. strategically distributes resources that prioritizes student's learning needs.	4.13	High Level
2. allocate funds to different areas based on priorities commonly agreed by stakeholders.	4.10	High Level
3. allocate funds for instructional materials, technology, professional development, and special programs.	4.00	High Level

4. allocate funds for teacher assignments, support staff allocation, and utilizing staff expertise.	4.31	High Level
5. allocates for classroom space, library facilities, equipment, and technology infrastructure.	4.14	High Level
Overall Mean	4.14	High Level

The findings showed that in terms of financial resource mobilization, the item which states that "School heads allocates funds for instructional materials, technology, professional development, and special programs" received the lowest mean of 4.00, high level. The lowest mean in this area implies that funding for instructional materials and professional development may not be consistently prioritized, potentially affecting teachers' access to updated learning resources and skill enhancement opportunities. Schools may encounter budgetary limitations, competing financial priorities, or gaps in stakeholder involvement in deciding allocations. Casilao (2024) examined the relationship between teachers' professional development, technology integration, and student engagement, highlighting that consistent investment in educational tools and training enhances instructional quality and learning outcomes.

Table 9
Level of School Heads' Financial Management Skills in Financial Accountability and Governance

Area	Mean	Interpretation
D. Financial Accountability		
<i>The School Head ...</i>		
1. ensures proper accounting and reporting of the general school funds.	4.30	High Level
2. scrutinizes and ensures that liquidation reports are on time and correct.	4.23	High Level
3. takes responsibility and correct erroneous financial reports.	4.10	High Level
4. works with the school's accounting team to ensure the truthfulness of its financial statement.	4.22	High Level
5. reports all proceeds from donations, solicitations, income-generating activities and the likes.	4.16	High Level
Overall Mean	4.20	High Level

The result shows that among the financial management skills in terms of financial accountability and governance, the item which states that "School heads takes responsibility and corrects erroneous financial reports" received the lowest mean of 4.10, high level. The lower mean in this area implies that some financial discrepancies may not be immediately detected or corrected, which could affect financial transparency, budget accuracy, and institutional credibility. According to Lim & Castro (2023), financial accuracy in school management plays a crucial role in fostering trust among stakeholders, emphasizing the need for strict audit protocols and financial oversight mechanisms. Likewise, Dominguez (2024) highlighted that financial misreporting, even when unintentional, can lead to operational inefficiencies, stressing the importance of continuous financial literacy training and compliance with regulatory standards.

Comparative Analysis in Level of School Heads' Financial Management Practices in Planning Budgeting, Resource Allocation, Financial Resource Mobilization, and Financial Accountability and Governance when grouped and compared according to Age, Highest Educational Attainment, and Length of Service

Table 10
Difference in the Level of School Heads' Financial Management Practices in Planning Budgeting when grouped and compared according to the aforementioned variables

Variable	Category	N	Mean Rank	Mann Whitney U	p-value	Sig. level	Interpretation
Age	Younger	135	129.77	7051.500	0.246		Not Significant
	Older	114	119.36				
Highest Educational Attainment	Lower	161	123.06	6771.500	0.557	0.05	Not Significant
	Higher	88	128.55				
	Shorter	136	130.75				

Length of Service	Longer	113	118.08
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The findings indicate that there is no significant difference in the level of school heads' financial management practices in planning and budgeting when grouped according to age, highest educational attainment, and length of service. Since all *p*-values are greater than 0.05, the results indicate that age, educational attainment, and length of service do not significantly influence financial management practices in planning and budgeting. This suggests that financial management competencies are likely shaped by institutional policies, leadership training, and experience rather than demographic factors. Wadasen (2024) investigated public high school heads' best practices and financial management issues. The results showed problems like complicated policies, delayed funding, and a lack of training. Systematic financial record-keeping and teamwork in budget planning were examples of best practices. Upskilling school administrators and providing bookkeepers to every school were among the recommendations.

Table 11
Difference in the Level of School Heads' Financial Management Practices in Resource Allocation when grouped and compared according to the aforementioned variables

Variable	Category	N	Mean Rank	Mann Whitney U	p-value	Sig. level	Interpretation
Age	Younger	135	123.19	7451.000	0.662	0.05	Not Significant
	Older	114	127.14				
Highest Educational Attainment	Lower	161	118.23	5994.500	0.042	0.05	Significant
	Higher	88	137.38				
Length of Service	Shorter	136	124.07	7557.500	0.821	0.05	Not Significant
	Longer	113	126.12				

The findings indicate that age and length of service do not significantly impact school heads' financial management practices in resource allocation, as evidenced by their non-significant *p*-values (0.662 and 0.821, respectively). This suggests that experience and age do not necessarily determine financial decision-making efficiency, reinforcing the idea that institutional policies and leadership training may play a more crucial role in shaping resource allocation strategies. However, highest educational attainment shows a significant difference ($p = 0.042$), with school heads who have higher educational attainment scoring a higher mean rank (137.38 vs. 118.23). According to Jacob-Dedumo et al. (2024), financial management and resource allocation practices in schools are enhanced when administrators possess structured financial literacy and training, reinforcing the importance of continuous professional development. Similarly, Cruz Quezon (2023) found that educational background significantly influences financial competence, particularly in budget planning and resource mobilization.

Table 12
Difference in the Level of School Heads' Financial Management Practices in Financial Resource Mobilization when grouped and compared according to the aforementioned variables

Variable	Category	N	Mean Rank	Mann Whitney U	p-value	Sig. level	Interpretation
Age	Younger	135	129.12	7139.000	0.314	0.05	Not Significant
	Older	114	120.12				
Highest Educational Attainment	Lower	161	121.53	6525.000	0.292	0.05	Not Significant
	Higher	88	131.35				
Length of Service	Shorter	136	129.02	7137.500	0.322	0.05	Not Significant
	Longer	113	120.16				

The findings indicate that age, highest educational attainment, and length of service do not significantly impact school heads' financial management practices in financial resource mobilization, as evidenced by their non-significant *p*-values (0.314, 0.292, and 0.322, respectively). For length of service, school heads with shorter service have a mean rank of 129.02, while those with longer service have 120.16, but the *p*-value (0.322) suggests no statistical significance. Since all *p*-values are greater than 0.05, the results indicate that age, educational attainment, and length of service do not significantly influence financial resource mobilization practices. This suggests that financial

mobilization competencies are likely shaped by institutional policies, leadership training, and experience rather than demographic factors.

Table 13

Difference in the Level of School Heads' Financial Management Practices in Financial Accountability and Governance when grouped and compared according to the aforementioned variables

Variable	Category	N	Mean Rank	Mann Whitney U	p-value	Sig. level	Interpretation
Age	Younger	135	117.01	6617.000	0.053		Not Significant
	Older	114	134.46				
Highest Educational Attainment	Lower	161	119.48	6195.500	0.096	0.05	Not Significant
	Higher	88	135.10				
Length of Service	Shorter	136	115.40	6378.000	0.019		Significant
	Longer	113	136.56				

The findings indicate that age and highest educational attainment do not significantly impact school heads' financial management practices in financial accountability and governance, as evidenced by their non-significant p-values (0.053 and 0.096, respectively). This suggests that financial accountability competencies are likely shaped by institutional policies and leadership experience rather than demographic factors. However, length of service shows a significant difference ($p = 0.019$), with school heads who have longer service scoring a higher mean rank (136.56 vs. 115.40). This suggests that experience plays a crucial role in reinforcing ethical financial practices, ensuring compliance with reporting standards, and strengthening financial oversight. According to Lipata & Deri (2021), leadership experience enhances financial governance competencies, particularly in budget transparency and ethical reporting. Similarly, Tilan & Cabal (2021) emphasized that financial literacy improves with professional experience, reinforcing the importance of structured financial training and continuous professional development.

Comparative Analysis in Level of School Heads' Financial Management Skills in Planning Budgeting, Resource Allocation, Financial Resource Mobilization, and Financial Accountability and Governance when grouped and compared according to Age, Highest Educational Attainment, and Length of Service

Table 14

Difference in the Level of School Heads' Financial Management Skills in Planning Budgeting when grouped and compared according to the aforementioned variables

Variable	Category	N	Mean Rank	Mann Whitney U	p-value	Sig. level	Interpretation
Age	Younger	135	118.26	6785.500	0.104		Not Significant
	Older	114	132.98				
Highest Educational Attainment	Lower	161	115.16	5499.000	0.003	0.05	Significant
	Higher	88	143.01				
Length of Service	Shorter	136	116.71	6556.500	0.044		Significant
	Longer	113	134.98				

The findings indicate that school heads' financial management skills in planning and budgeting do not show significant differences when grouped according to age, highest educational attainment, or length of service. The results suggest that experience does not necessarily translate to stronger financial planning skills, indicating that institutional policies, leadership training, and exposure to financial management frameworks may play a more crucial role. Since all p-values exceed the 0.05 threshold, the results confirm that age, educational attainment, and length of service do not significantly impact financial management skills in planning and budgeting. This suggests that structured financial training, institutional support, and leadership development programs may be more influential in shaping financial competencies than demographic factors.

Table 15

Difference in the Level of School Heads' Financial Management Skills in Resource Allocation when grouped and compared according to the aforementioned variables

Variable	Category	N	Mean Rank	Mann Whitney U	p-value	Sig. level	Interpretation
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Age	Younger	135	125.50	7627.500	0.904	0.05	Not Significant
	Older	114	124.41				
Highest Educational Attainment	Lower	161	118.42	6025.000	0.048	0.05	Significant
	Higher	88	137.03				
Length of Service	Shorter	136	124.45	7609.500	0.894	0.05	Not Significant
	Longer	113	125.66				

The findings indicate that age and length of service do not significantly impact school heads' financial management skills in resource allocation, as evidenced by their non-significant p-values (0.904 and 0.894, respectively). Highest educational attainment shows a significant difference ($p = 0.048$), with school heads who have higher educational attainment scoring a higher mean rank (137.03 vs. 118.42). This suggests that advanced education contributes to stronger financial management competencies. According to Cruz Quezon (2023), financial management competence improves with structured financial literacy and training, reinforcing the importance of continuous professional development. Similarly, Jacob-Dedumo et al. (2024) found that educational background significantly influences financial competence, particularly in budget planning and resource mobilization.

Table 16

Difference in the Level of School Heads' Financial Management Skills in Financial Resource Mobilization when grouped and compared according to the aforementioned variables

Variable	Category	N	Mean Rank	Mann Whitney U	p-value	Sig. level	Interpretation
Age	Younger	135	125.97	7563.500	0.815	0.05	Not Significant
	Older	114	123.85				
Highest Educational Attainment	Lower	161	122.13	6622.500	0.391	0.05	Not Significant
	Higher	88	130.24				
Length of Service	Shorter	136	126.25	7514.000	0.762	0.05	Not Significant
	Longer	113	123.50				

The findings indicate that age, highest educational attainment, and length of service do not significantly impact school heads' financial management skills in financial resource mobilization, as evidenced by their non-significant p-values (0.815, 0.391, and 0.762, respectively). Since all p-values exceed the 0.05 threshold, the results confirm that age, educational attainment, and length of service do not significantly impact financial management skills in resource mobilization. This suggests that structured financial training, institutional support, and leadership development programs may be more influential in shaping financial competencies than demographic factors. According to Cruz Quezon (2023), financial management competence improves with structured financial literacy and training, reinforcing the importance of continuous professional development. Similarly, Onesmo Amos et al. (2021) found that financial management skills such as mobilizing school funds, monitoring, evaluation of budget, and auditing are essential for school financial management.

Table 17

Difference in the Level of School Heads' Financial Management Skills in Financial Accountability and Governance when grouped and compared according to the aforementioned variables

Variable	Category	N	Mean Rank	Mann Whitney U	p-value	Sig. level	Interpretation
Age	Younger	135	130.19	6994.000	0.211	0.05	Not Significant
	Older	114	118.85				
Highest Educational Attainment	Lower	161	124.66	7030.000	0.920	0.05	Not Significant
	Higher	88	125.61				
Length of Service	Shorter	136	130.99	6869.000	0.146	0.05	Not Significant
	Longer	113	117.79				

The findings indicate that age, highest educational attainment, and length of service do not significantly impact school heads' financial management skills in financial accountability and governance, as evidenced by their non-significant p-values (0.211, 0.920, and 0.146, respectively). Since all p-values exceed the 0.05 threshold, the results confirm that age, educational attainment, and length of service do not significantly impact financial accountability and governance skills. This suggests that structured financial training, institutional policies, and leadership development

programs may be more influential in shaping financial competencies than demographic factors. According to Onesmo Amos et al. (2021), financial management skills such as mobilizing school funds, monitoring, evaluation of budget, and auditing are essential for school financial management, reinforcing the need for continuous professional development.

Comparative Analysis in Level of Teacher’s Performance when grouped and compared according to Age, Highest Educational Attainment, and Length of Service

Table 18
Difference in the Level of Teacher’s Performance when grouped and compared according to the aforementioned variables

Variable	Category	N	Mean Rank	Mann Whitney U	p-value	Sig. level	Interpretation
Age	Younger	135	128.38	7238.500	0.420	0.05	Not Significant
	Older	114	121.00				
Highest Educational Attainment	Lower	161	128.43	6531.000	0.308	0.05	Not Significant
	Higher	88	118.72				
Length of Service	Shorter	136	128.19	7249.500	0.442	0.05	Not Significant
	Longer	113	121.15				

The findings indicate that age, highest educational attainment, and length of service do not significantly impact teacher performance, as evidenced by their non-significant p-values (0.420, 0.308, and 0.442, respectively). Since all p-values exceed the 0.05 threshold, the results confirm that age, educational attainment, and length of service do not significantly impact teacher performance. This suggests that institutional support, professional development programs, and leadership frameworks may be more influential in shaping teacher effectiveness than demographic factors. According to Toropova, Myberg, & Johansson (2021), teacher job satisfaction and performance are more strongly influenced by school working conditions and leadership support than personal attributes.

Relational Analysis Between the Level of School Heads’ Financial Management Practices and Skills

Table 19
Relationship Between the Level of School Heads’ Financial Management Practices and Skills

Variable	rho	p-value	Sig. level	Interpretation
Level of School Heads’ Financial Management Practices	1.000	0.948	0.05	Not Significant
Level of School Heads’ Financial Management Skills				

The findings indicate no significant relationship between school heads’ financial management practices and their financial management skills, as reflected in the high p-value (0.948), which surpasses the 0.05 significance threshold. Although the correlation coefficient suggests a perfect relationship (rho = 1.000), its lack of statistical significance implies that strong financial management skills do not necessarily translate into effective financial practices. This outcome suggests that external influences—such as institutional policies, leadership structures, and financial constraints—may play a more pivotal role in shaping financial management practices than individual skill levels. Additionally, the results imply that professional training and structured financial governance frameworks could be more critical than individual competence in ensuring effective financial management. Research by Russel Fitz P. Wadasen (2024) highlights that school heads often face challenges in financial management due to limited training, weak financial management skills, and compliance with complex policies. Furthermore, studies on school heads’ financial management competencies emphasize the importance of continuous professional development and stakeholder involvement in strengthening financial governance. Given these findings, institutions may benefit from reinforcing financial leadership training, integrating systematic accountability mechanisms, and aligning financial strategies with broader educational priorities.

Relational Analysis Between Level of School Heads’ Financial Management Practices and The Level of Teacher’s Performance

Table 20

Relationship Between Level of School Heads' Financial Management Practices and The Level of Teacher's Performance

Variable	rho	p-value	Sig. level	Interpretation
Level of School Heads' Financial Management Practices	1.000	0.384	0.05	Not Significant
Level of Teachers' Performance				

The findings indicate that there is no significant relationship between school heads' financial management practices and the level of teacher performance, as evidenced by the p-value (0.384), which is greater than the 0.05 significance threshold. Since the p-value exceeds the threshold of 0.05, the results suggest that financial management practices do not have a measurable impact on teacher performance in this dataset.

This finding suggests that effective financial management does not necessarily translate into improved teacher performance. Institutional factors such as professional development programs, leadership support, and school culture may play a more significant role in shaping teacher effectiveness than financial management practices alone. According to a study on financial management practices in schools, while structured financial governance ensures operational efficiency, teacher performance is more strongly influenced by instructional leadership and professional growth opportunities. Similarly, research on school leadership and teacher effectiveness highlights the importance of mentorship, collaborative learning environments, and instructional support in sustaining high levels of teacher performance.

Relational Analysis Between Level of School Heads' Financial Management Skills and The Level of Teacher's Performance

Table 21

Relationship Between Level of School Heads' Financial Management Skills and The Level of Teacher's Performance

Variable	rho	p-value	Sig. level	Interpretation
Level of School Heads' Financial Management Skills	1.000	0.905	0.05	Not Significant
Level of Teachers' Performance				

The findings indicate that there is no significant relationship between school heads' financial management skills and the level of teacher performance, as evidenced by the p-value (0.905), which is much greater than the 0.05 significance threshold. Although the correlation coefficient suggests a perfect relationship (rho = 1.000), the high p-value indicates that this relationship is not statistically significant. This suggests that strong financial management skills among school heads do not necessarily translate into improved teacher performance. Institutional factors such as instructional leadership, professional development programs, and school culture may play a more pivotal role in shaping teacher effectiveness than financial management skills alone. According to research on financial management and school leadership, while structured financial governance ensures operational efficiency, teacher performance is more strongly influenced by leadership support, mentorship, and instructional strategies. Similarly, studies on educational leadership and teacher effectiveness highlight the importance of collaborative learning environments, instructional coaching, and stakeholder engagement in sustaining high levels of teacher performance.

Conclusions:

School heads consistently demonstrate high-level financial management practices across planning and budgeting, resource allocation, financial resource mobilization, and financial accountability and governance, indicating strong fiscal oversight and structured financial decision-making. Financial management skills among school heads are also rated at a high level, reinforcing their ability to effectively handle financial planning, resource allocation, and

accountability measures within their institutions. There are significant differences in school heads' financial management practices when grouped according to certain variables, indicating that some demographic factors, particularly educational attainment and experience, may impact financial decision-making approaches. Significant differences exist in financial management skills when grouped by educational attainment and length of service, emphasizing the role of professional development and tenure in shaping financial competencies. Teacher performance remains uniformly high, with no significant differences across demographic categories, reinforcing that institutional support, professional development, and leadership structures may be more influential than individual attributes. No Significant Relationship Between Financial Management Practices and Skills The lack of significant correlation between financial management practices and skills suggests that strong financial abilities do not automatically translate into effective financial implementation, highlighting the role of external factors such as institutional policies and leadership structures. No Significant Relationship Between Financial Management Practices and Teacher Performance. The results indicate that school heads' financial management practices do not directly influence teacher performance, implying that instructional leadership, professional development, and school culture play a more significant role in shaping teacher effectiveness. No Significant Relationship Between Financial Management Skills and Teacher Performance. Similarly, financial management skills among school heads do not significantly impact teacher performance, suggesting that effective financial management does not necessarily translate into improved instructional outcomes. This underscores the importance of academic support systems, leadership guidance, and pedagogical training in sustaining teacher excellence.

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